

EDUCATIONAL DIFFERENCE BETWEEN USA AND UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10389544>

Anotation: This article explores the notable differences in the education systems between the United States and Uzbekistan. It delves into various aspects such as teaching methodologies, approaches to plagiarism, professorial roles, student autonomy, and the overall structure of education in both countries. The examination aims to shed light on the distinct features characterizing each system, providing insights into how they contribute to shaping the academic landscape and influencing student experiences.

Key words:

Education Systems, United States, Uzbekistan, Disparities, Teaching Methodologies, Plagiarism, Professorial Roles, Student Autonomy, Academic Structure, Comparative Analys.

The distinction between our educational system and that of the United States lies in the emphasis on reading. In the US, both students and professors engage extensively with books, staying informed about new publications and research in their respective fields. This stands in contrast to our insular approach, where a lack of awareness hinders our connection to global advancements. Instead of contributing novel ideas, we often rely on outdated reports circulated within Uzbekistan, highlighting the need for corrective measures.

The detrimental impact of plagiarism on academic careers is a significant concern. Tasked with reviewing local PhD dissertations, I've observed a prevalence of defended theses with low scientific value. Individuals attain scientific titles by translating content from the Soviet era or other languages without proper references, creating a landscape where non-existent citations proliferate. In the US, a stringent system promptly detects plagiarism, resulting in automatic failure for those who fail to provide references. The grave consequences emphasize the urgency of addressing plagiarism for the advancement of science and innovation.

The role of a professor differs significantly between our system and that of the US. In the US, being a professor is not merely a title but a position with associated salaries and benefits. Professors deliver lectures for various academic levels, from bachelor's to doctoral students, and are not confined to traditional office spaces. Many prefer working from home, where they can focus on research and publications without distractions. Their performance, including research output, article and book publications, contributes to the university's prestige, influencing students' decisions when choosing educational institutions. This contrasts with our system, where the professorial title lacks the same level of institutional support and recognition.

Students pursue subjects of their passion. Upon graduating from the Institute of Oriental Studies, where our education followed a strict schedule, I noticed a contrasting approach in the United States. While freshmen have mandatory courses, from the second year onward, students delve into specialties they find appealing, creating their own academic programs. The educational focus goes beyond rote memorization. Unlike my past experience of writing down lectures, in the US, a structured lesson plan known as a 'syllabus' guides each class. This

document serves as the primary conduit between teachers and students, promoting independent learning. Students don't seek constant guidance but engage with weekly readings from esteemed sources instead of relying on textbooks.

In my classes with students in their second, third, and fourth years, they tackle 100 pages weekly as a standard assignment for a single lesson. Balancing a minimum of five courses simultaneously, they demonstrate their preparation by discussing the assigned material, emphasizing critical analysis over mere recitation.

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3. College Board: - Website: [College Board](<https://www.collegeboard.org/>) Known for administering standardized tests like the SAT, the College Board also provides resources on college planning, admissions, and financial aid.
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